

8T – Higgs Mass Series and the Gamma Bosons

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October 27, 2021

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Introduction

The 8T is a variational manifold setting consisting of the main equations. The first equation describes the Einstein manifold invoked stationary by the Euler Lagrange operator. This equation validates the idea of the equivalence principle between Gravity and acceleration.

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_m} \frac{\partial s_m}{\partial M_E} \frac{\partial M_E}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g_m}{\partial t_m} \delta g_m - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M_E} \frac{\partial M_E}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g_n}{\partial t_n} \delta g_n = 0 \quad (1)$$

the two equations (1.1) and (1.2) are representing the set of ideas, which yielded the primordial coupling series. The form of (1.2) presented in this type is the "type form" primordial which takes the prime multiplier to present an index of variants within each interaction.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1.1)$$

$$\left(2e^- * \prod_{i=1}^{i=N_V} \Psi_i + e^-_{\mu} \right) + N_{V\mu} = 30:128:850:9254 \dots \quad (1.2)$$

$$\prod_{i=1}^{i=N_V} \Psi_i = +N_{V\mu}$$

Higgs Mass

This section the author will postulate a set of theorems and ideas to answer the question of the Higgs mass, and in addition trying to eliminate this free parameter by predicting the masses of the other Higgs particles using the Primorial coupling constants setting. The setting will use the spin formation.

Theorem (1): Higgs mass creation is related to a symmetry break within the spin zero term.

Theorem (2): Spin symmetry break is due to an additional term.

Theorem (2.1): The additional term must be non-vanishing, i.e. a prime.

Theorem (3): The prime must be proportional to the term itself.

The spin formation of the main equation:

Spin 0: $2N_0$ variations

Spin $\frac{1}{2}$: $2N_0 + 3$ variations

Spin 1: $2N_0 + 3 + N_V$ variations

Spin $N = 2N_0 + 3 + N_{V1} + N_{V2} \dots$ variations

Since the Higgs is spin zero, the terms which represent this object are the following marked in black:

8 + (1)

$$[(\mathbf{8} \times \mathbf{3}) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(\mathbf{24} \times \mathbf{5}) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(\mathbf{120} \times \mathbf{7}) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

Since there is no need for the higher terms of spin for the analysis of this paper, the author will eliminate them.

$$2N_0 = 8$$

$$2N_1 = (8 \times 3)$$

$$2N_2 = (24 \times 5)$$

When the invariant three appears from the second term and above, it appears outside of the parenthesis and term is presenting the massive Bosons as it is isomorphic to the Lepton. Now the same idea will be used inside the spin zero using the first theorem. Since the first term does not have a corresponding prime, the symmetry does not break and it will be manifested as a massless scalar field.

$$H_0 = 0 \text{ GeV}$$

Their symmetry will break from the second term and above. For the first term symmetry break, using the rest three theorems, the prime must be proportional to the term, appear inside the zero spin term parenthesis and its non-vanishing nature due to it being a prime, will ensure the mass would be present for all temporal segment.

$$(8 \times 3 + 3) = 27$$

The mass of the second Higgs would stand as

$$H_1 = 27 \text{ GeV}$$

The second coupling term, symmetry break:

$$(24 \times 5 + 5) = 125$$

The mass of the third Higgs would stand as:

$$H_2 = 125 \text{ GeV}$$

The mass of the rest, assuming eight distinct Higgs particle given by the type representation of the first coupling term:

$$8 + (1)$$

Which is the only term that does not involve the invariant three and thus spin one-half, i.e. the only term which is naturally correlated to spin zero. The right element in each term is representing the variants count of each interaction that is the idea used to state there exist eight Gluon fields.

$$8 \times 1 = 1 \times 8$$

The higher Higgs particle index is, the higher masses it should have innately contain. The overall series predicted eight Higgs particles, one massless, seven heavy:

$$H_0 = 0 \text{ GeV}$$

$$H_1 = 27 \text{ GeV}$$

$$H_2 = 125 \text{ GeV}$$

$$H_3 = 847 \text{ GeV}$$

$$H_4 = 9251 \text{ GeV}$$

$$H_5 = 120,133 \text{ GeV}$$

$$H_6 = 2,042,057 \text{ GeV}$$

$$H_7 = 38,798,779 \text{ GeV}$$

We already know there exist a massless scalar field, which is the Goldstone Boson if one is correct, and the prediction of the third term is accurate with experiment. Any other prediction of masses in between the first and third or higher index than the third would validate the idea to a greater extent as one measured value is far from enough, at least two are needed. The idea and the direction of the series seems to be coming in agreement with the fact that the mass of the Higgs considered light. summing up, mass creation of spin zero particle is theorized to be a result of an additional element appearing in the zero spin term, causing it to account mass. The term is prime, i.e. non-vanishing, and it was taken from the primordial which given the appearance of the invariant three, resulting in the appearance of massive Gauge Bosons, where before the Gluon with only two terms are massless. Additional term account for massive mass, inside the term of spin zero. To put the idea in rigor, the Higgs mass is a result of a symmetry break of the form:

$$(2N_{0 \rightarrow K} + N_V)$$

$$N_V \propto 2N_{0 \rightarrow K}$$

Higgs Decay

By retaining the original form of the spin zero, i.e. the form:

$$2N_{0 \rightarrow K}$$

Which represent an even amount of variations, which is taken to zero given no other terms such as the invariant three:

$$((2N_{0 \rightarrow K} = 0) \forall k)$$

So there exist a spectra of decay, it could decay to matter anti matter pairs, which also vanish into zero. It could vanish to an even number which than will decompose to odd number of Bosons. As few examples:

$$2N_{0 \rightarrow K} \rightarrow e^- e^+$$

$$2N_{0 \rightarrow K} \rightarrow W^- W^+$$

$$2N_{0 \rightarrow K} \rightarrow (\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 + \dots \delta g_l)$$

Since the mass of this particle is relativity high, it would be more reasonable to assume that the particle would decay to heavier particles with similar mass range. Making that less likely to decay to light mass as the first family, when considering decay to matter. When considering decay to Bosons, the Heavy bosons of the weak interaction are the most reasonable option, as they possess mass compared to Gluons or photons. If the Bosonic mass pattern is correct, the Gamma Boson should possess mass as well, which makes the author to predict that Higgs could decay to this new exotic Gamma Boson. To predict the mass of the Gamma Boson the author will postulate a theorem:

The \mathcal{M} theorem: The magnitude of mass is proportional to the prime element of net variation.

That means that for the Weak coupling term takes the form:

$$[(\mathbf{8} \times \mathbf{3}) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow [(\mathbf{8} \times \mathbf{3}) + (e^-)] + W^-$$

The mass of the Weak interaction Boson is proportional to the net variation

$$(W_{\mathcal{M}}^{\pm}) \propto (3) \cong 80.3 \text{ GeV}$$

$$(Z_{\mathcal{M}}^0) \propto (3) \cong 91.2 \text{ GeV}$$

Let the subscript denote the mass feature of the particle. For the Gamma Boson:

$$((\mathbf{120} \times \mathbf{7}) + (3)) + 7 \rightarrow [(\mathbf{120} \times \mathbf{7}) + (e^-)] + \Gamma_{\mu}^i$$

$$(\Gamma_{\mu}^i)_{\mathcal{M}} \propto (7)$$

$$1 \leq i \leq 7$$

For clarification, μ denote the five-vector, the diverging curvature over spatial dimensions, the superscript i denoting the count of the seven type Gamma Bosons predicted to exist and the \mathcal{M} is indicating the mass feature.

$$\frac{(7)}{(3)} \cong 2.333$$

The Gamma Bosons mass range than should account for:

$$2.333 \times 80.3 \leq (\Gamma_\mu^i)_M \leq 2.333 \times 91.2$$

$$186.66 \text{ GeV} \leq (\Gamma_\mu^i)_M \leq 212.33 \text{ GeV}$$

Making the Gamma Bosons range possible decay of the next Higgs in the series.

$$H_3 \rightarrow \Gamma_\mu^i$$

At the mass range of that Higgs, approximately four Gamma Bosons can be produced as a result.

$$\frac{H_3}{(\Gamma_\mu^i)_M} \cong 4$$

Updating the index:

$$H_3 \rightarrow \Gamma_\mu^{i=4}$$

Indexing using the superscript in such way is improving the length of notation, which instead of writing the produced particles in linear terms as:

$$H_3 \rightarrow \Gamma_\mu \Gamma_\mu \Gamma_\mu \Gamma_\mu$$

$$H_3 \rightarrow (\Gamma \Gamma \Gamma \Gamma)_\mu$$

they are contained in one term. The superscript also does not indicate which particles the Higgs decayed onto, making it more general statement and thus much better as many compositions are allowed.

Higgs Self Interaction

In the Lagrangian of the Higgs in Quantum field theories, there is a term that describe the interaction of the Higgs with itself. This section will aspire to describe the phenomena of this interaction. Since The Higgs relate to terms which are scalar multiplies of each other, it is possible to claim that each higher interaction Boson is the same interaction, which interact with itself via the scalar. Or to put it in rigor:

$$2N_n = 2N_0 \times \Phi_1 \times \Phi_2 \dots \times \Phi_n$$

Alternatively:

$$2N_n = 2^{e^-} \times \Phi_1 \times \Phi_2 \dots \times \Phi_n$$

Where the set:

$$\Phi_{1 \rightarrow n} \in \mathbb{R}$$

Where the 2^{e^-} denote the invariant massless Higgs Boson as it does not correspond to a prime, so it's symmetry does not break.

Higgs on VC Framework

The purpose of that section is to describe the phenomena of the Higgs using the framework of variational curvature. The emphasis will not be on rigor, but on ideas. Since the Higgs is classed as a Boson, it is a certain amount of curvature on the manifold. During the interaction with other elements, this element called the Higgs is inserting certain amount of curvature onto the Bosons, synonymous with inserting a mass. Since the Higgs is considered a scalar, it has a unique feature. If one is correct, the Higgs could be thought as a standing curvature rather than diverging curvature, as a diverging curvature coming across this standing curvature, some of the standing curvature is being inserted into the diverging ripple and by doing so the mass is being inserted. By the modern variation of the forces and accelerations present in the first part of the thesis, since the Fermions are also in a sense standing potential curvature, there should be an interaction between the Higgs field and the Fermion sector. The main idea is correlating the standing curvature to the Higgs field, and using the opposite traits of diverging curvature meeting standing curvature as means to explain how mass is formulated. There are more than few open questions such as the reason the Photon does not couple into the Higgs while the Bosons of the Weak interaction do.

Forms of Symmetry Break

This idea seems to manifest itself in several forms. The first form was used back in the day, in early 2021, when the coupling series was first derived and the enigma of the invariant three was analyzed, which one regard it as an additional term which broke the symmetry of the coupling series. The term at the time was considered a "destabilizer" of the series. The second form of symmetry break was when a vanishing from of variations, such as eight multiplies is mutated toward a certain direction. The plus toward a Boson diverging, short or long ranged, and the minus toward an insertion of mass. The minus was used to derive the Quark masses series, which now seems to be only partly correct as there exist a limitation for the number of Electrons. Thus, the devisors must not exceed the third family. The last form of symmetry break is the most recent and it is correlated to the insertion of an additional element to the zero spin terms in the primorial, as means to break the symmetry of the Higgs itself. Assuming there exist eight Gauge fields, one massless, and seven with increasing mass order. That series include a Boson with the observed mass, which is the third Boson in the series, and the second with mass. Summing up, symmetry break takes the same form in different contexts, and is related to a spontaneous appearing of an additional element. The element can be positive or negative. The placement of this element on the primorial is determining which symmetry break there is. If it is within the zero spin term, the symmetry break is getting the mass to the Higgs. If it is outside, it is the symmetry break on the Bosons. In the more general form, symmetry break of a plus sign than it is correlated to diverging curvature or force, whereas a minus sign is of a mass generation. Since the Higgs is standing curvature which is responsible for mass generation on Bosons and Fermions, it should be considered as $8 - (1)$. So to make things clear, the Higgs is of the form of mass generator:

$$8 - (1)$$

Which leads to cancelation of the Destabilizer marked in black:

$$2N_{0 \rightarrow K} + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2}$$

Leading to the term:

$$2N_{0 \rightarrow K}$$

Now note that the sole term is massless. From here, it is possible to incorporate the idea of the spin zero term breaking, by adding an additional term inside the spin zero term, which is proportional to prime sequence. That was the idea above which lead to the series of the eight Higgs particles, seven heavy one massless, i.e. the first. Third Higgs with mass matched the observed value measured, as far as one knows it was 125.35 GeV by CMS collaboration:

$$\frac{125}{125.35} = 99.72$$

Which is about one hundred percent accurate. But in order to make sure the idea is correct, at least one of the other Higgs should be found, as it could be just a coincidence. "Best" case would be lighter Higgs, 27 GeV and the corresponding heavier Higgs, i.e. the 847 GeV validating the idea of the Higgs series.

Higgs as Universal Quantity

This idea of universal quantity meant to express that the Higgs masses are invariant across the packet. That is because according to the idea and the four theorems made, the symmetry breaking causing to mass accumulation on the Higgs is prime related, and prime proportional on each term. Taking into account that the prime ring is universe invariant, each universe must have the same Higgs particles, both in kind and in mass. If the same Higgs particles are related to the observed particles masses, both in the Boson sector and the Fermion sector, the conclusion is that the same masses must appear at all universes across the packet. The question of how exactly does the Higgs inserting the masses is still vague, i.e. why the coupling to the Higgs are what they are. The author will attempt to put this new ideas in rigor. Assuming Higgs is mass generator:

$$X(8 - (1))$$

While the Bosons are diverging curvature ripple:

$$\zeta(8 + (1))$$

Let:

$$X(8 - (1)) + \zeta(8 + (1)) = -\lambda^{1 \rightarrow k}$$

Or

$$X \gg \zeta$$

The difference in the above multipliers leading to a set of parameter, by requiring that the amount of standing curvature to exceed the diverging curvature, it is possible to create an insertion on the diverging ripple. That insertion is the mass absorbed onto the ripple. The set of masses is manifold invariant which is in agreement with the \mathcal{L} theorem, assuming there exist only one set of Higgs particles across the manifold packet. The 8T would like to create a setting in which all particles appear exactly the same way, in the same way across the packet, given by this theorem. If the Higgs is universal property given by the prime symmetry break that the mission is accomplished as the question of the masses was the last question needed for reaching that objective. Fermions are manifold invariant as they are the result of stationary manifold condition, which is imposed over all the manifolds in the packet. The Bosons are invariant across the packet as they are primes, and the prime ring is manifold invariant, and the last pillar was the question of the masses, which can be solved by the above idea. First ensuring the Higgs is manifold invariant by the prime sequence and using it to develop the trait of similar observed mass for Both Fermion and Bosons.

It was known long before the 8T was constructed that nature is "satisfied with simplicity" as Newton stated, and that is what is presented here. It is rather complicated to generate set of new particles with new masses for each universe, or a new set of laws, rather than using one set of laws for all. Similar to there is no special direction in space, there should be no special universe in the packet, they must obey the same laws. If one is allowed to create new version for Newton statement on simplicity, it would be by replacing the simplicity with the word "minima" or "extremums".

References

[1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

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